

Review Article

Falsification of Raw Herbal Trades: Identification Tools from Conventional to Modern Techniques

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Abstract

Wildlife forensics deals with the identification of the species from any trace amount of biological material, which also includes raw herbal trades, food products, herbal medicinal products along with the concerns of adulteration and admixtures of similar species. adulteration may be of different types, which may be deliberate or accidental. This article provides comprehensive information on the techniques available for resolving adulteration issues along with suitable case studies. We discuss the variety of techniques (simple and sophisticated, costlier and economical) and their application in identifying adulterants from genuine materials.

Keywords – Plant forensic, Medicinal plant, Adulteration, and Identification techniques.

Introduction

Since ancient times, India has rich diversity of medicinal plants due to the variation in meteorological conditions from East to West and North to South. Due to the diversity of medicinal plants, it has a long history of traditional medicinal practices [1]. In India around 6000 plant species are used in several folk healthcare medicines, estimates suggest that around 9500-registered herbal industries depend on the resource of medicinal plants for manufacturing raw herbal products [2]. It also has various demands in large- commercial use in industries like food, medicines, weaving, perfumes, cosmetic products and ornaments. However, a primary concern in the use of herbal raw drugs is lack of accountability and confusion between legal trade and illegal trade, sustainable and unsustainable, of which many may go unreported [3]. Secondary concern is, as like animals (wild vs domesticated, in fact, most of the wild animals are not permitted to be domesticate), there is no proper distinction from wild plants and nursery or *in vitro* based plants. CITES has permitted nursery and *in vitro* plants for trade according to its IUCN status of particular species. Accordingly, plants collected from wild is restricted [4] and third major concern is about food and medicinal products frauds involved in finished packed products and mixing of the whole plant with similar morphological species as adulterant were supplied to various industries [5]. Therefore, it is a difficult task to predict the plant species and its adulterants or the products origin and

ingredients actually present in the products. Which can be a real challenge in the form of live plants, roots, cultures, seeds, dried plants, derivatives, flowers, stems, specimens, leaves, bulb or tuber, powder, wood nugget, wood product-complete processing, fruit or confectionary, aroma products-oil, fragrance, health products, food, dietary supplement, nutraceutical, functional food, and Cosmetics-skincare.

Plants from the wild normally weighed down by adulterations intentionally or unintentionally (substitution). Species substitution will adversely affect consumer health as it could cause severe allergies and other health consequences. Visual detection of species adulteration in the raw herbal trade is often difficult, as the plants are usually in a dry state and do not retain the original features of the plant [6-10]. Although identification protocols available and standardized for few but protocols for each and every specific plant and its adulterant is lacking. Thus, starting from classic techniques like Macroscopy, Microscopy, Physiochemical Parameters, Phytochemical analysis, to modern techniques like HPLC, DNA Barcoding, Genotyping and Metabarcodeing should be developed and practiced for individual species identification and its origin in the aspect of plant forensics [11-12]. Therefore, our study is aimed to provide a collective references of extensive case studies available on adulteration issues and varies techniques (classic to modern) used for the appropriate identification of adulterations.

1. Macroscopy

Macroscopy can also be named as morphology or organoleptic techniques that are in practice since ancient times. It is a widely used technique to understand and identify the genuineness from falsification along with the quality of particular medicinal plant or raw herbal material with a help of appearance, colour, odour, taste, size, shape and surface characteristics [13–15]. For example, flowers of *Viola odorata* (sold as Banafsha) are adulterated with *Viola pilosa* and *Viola betonicifolia*, thus to sort out such issues simple macroscopy field techniques can be used by observing the style and stigma. Style are inflated, broad and smooth in *Viola odorata*. Whereas in adulterant *Viola pilosa* the style would be shortly beaked at the apex and in *Viola betonicifolia* it will have hump like structure with lateral side opening [16]. Common Indian Bay leaf (*Cinnamomum tamala*) also reportedly adulterated with *Cinnamomum malabattrum*. The adulterant can be easily identified by the variation in size of the leaf and petiole, leaf margins, glabrous surface, and venation reaching up to the tip and taste more mucilaginous in contrast to that of *C. tamala* (Fig-1) [17].

Figure.1

Genuine Bay leaf *Cinnamomum tamala* adulterated with *Cinnamomum malabatrum*

Image Source: Kumar 2013

Similarly, willow leaf, swallow wort rhizome (*Cynanchi stauntonii*), and blackened swallow wort root (*Cynanchi atrati*) are often confused with each other due to similarity in their morphological characteristics (Fig. 2). The rhizome of the former grows horizontally and with a hollow at the center, while the root of the latter grows vertically with a solid center portion. These two species can thus be distinguished visually. [18]

A one more such case study is the adulteration reported for *Magnolia champaca*, where the strongly aromatic flowers of the genuine material are adulterated/substituted with the less aromatic flowers of *Magnolia baillonii*. This adulterant can be easily identified by the presence of bracts, sender and long pedicel, and the dark brown bracts that are more in number than the genuine material [43]

Figure.2

Genuine flowers of *Magnolia champaca* adulterated with *Magnolia baillonii*

Image Source: Nehru et al. 2014

2. Microscopy

The microscope is an important tool, used to restructure a crime, even trace evidence that may make or break a case. For this reason, microscopes are essential in many investigative purposes, because they can magnify an object in great detail. They may be used to check the striations on bullets to determine the type of gun used in a crime or it can also be used to compare hairs, fibres or other particulates recovered from the scene. Thus, plant materials found as adulterant, plants found in a crime scene can make lot of sense to make a case stronger [19]. The stem bark of *Saraca asoca* commonly known as asoka, is used as a principal constituent of several ayurvedic preparations. The commonly used adulterant is the bark of *Polyalthia longifolia* which shows some similarity with that of asoka. Simple comparative hand sections of both the species can reveal the identity of the material by clear differences in the epidermal and cortical cells [20]. Stem anatomical studies can easily differentiate the two confusing species of Piper namely *Piper colubrinum* and *Piper nigrum* [21]. *Cassia angustifolia* and its substitute *Cassia obtusifolia* can be identified with leaf anatomical studies [22]. About twenty-one species for *Ephedra* can be differentiated by the vessel types in well-developed aerial parts of all Chinese and North american species of *Ephedra* [23]. *Valeriana procera* (Mexican Valerian) is a commercially important species, sometimes used as a substitute for *Valeriana officinalis*, an important sedative in herbal medicine. A detailed microscopic account prepared for *V. procera* (both wild and cultivated) and other commercially important Valerian species such as *V. jatamansi*, *Valeriana edulis*, and *V. sitchensis* have provided a much needed microscopic details to differentiate these species from the original *V. officinalis* [24]. Many such examples could be found for the effective application of microscopy in identifying the adulteration. For example, microscopy observations revealed that the chili powder was adulterated with the fragments of plant straws, foliage and other substances; the pepper powder was adulterated with starch, straws and monosodium glutamate as well as some other substances; cumin and mustard powders were adulterated with straws and starch, etc. Such case studies prove the effectiveness of microscopic analysis in accurately determining the adulterants even from powder formations [25]. Also, in liquids like honey, microscopy can be an effective tool to determine the adulteration of normal sugar (derived from sugarcane) by detecting the presence of parenchyma cells, single rings of ring vessels and epidermal cells [26].

3. Physico-Chemical and Biochemical Methods

The physicochemical parameters are mainly used in judging the purity and quality of the products and investigating of chemical compounds from the available material on the physical properties of molecules and compounds, the reactivities and reaction mechanisms [44].

If adulterants used are of gum, resin, alum, starch, etc. starting with simple fire testing, water testing and settles down testing (*Sparganii rhizoma* and *Scirpi yagarae rhizoma* after being submerged in water Fig. 3) can instantly reveal the legitimacy of the product [18]. These minor techniques can be used as instant technique in the field to clear the doubt of suspected plant materials to differentiate from its adulterant, like artificial colourings and falsification, etc. For example, the original camphor floats & burns quickly [27 -29]. Also, the original camphor dilutes very quickly in Chloroform or solvent ether, but adulterated may dilute slowly [30].

Figure.3

Genuine Rhizome *Sparganii Rhizoma* submerged and *Scirpi Yagarae Rhizoma*-floating

Image Source- Zhao et al. 2011

There are other advanced methods for detection of adulterants which involve the use of basic to advance laboratory instruments, for example, High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), Gas Chromatography (GC); Spectroscopy - Mass Spectroscopy (MS), Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (NIR), Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR) and Atomic absorption Spectrometry (AAS); Immunology - Enzyme-Linked Immune-sorbent assay (ELISA); and, Electrophoresis [31].

Gas chromatography and Mass spectroscopy are proven to be useful in identifying the adulteration in therapeutic oils and essential oils. These oils are usually adulterated with:

vegetable carrier oils, alcohol, synthetic oils used as diluents, cheaper oils of the same species but of different geographical origins, cheaper essential oils extracted from another part of the plant, cheaper essential oils from related species and isolated natural, or (semi) synthetic compounds etc. [32-33]. *Ginkgo biloba* is a highly used herbal supplements, stems and leaf extracts provides positive effect on memory and the circulatory system, and the same is subjected to adulteration with flavonoids to meet the requirement of 24 % flavonol glycosides. Chemical analysis by ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry can efficiently detect such oil adulteration to identify the adulteration of ginkgo stem and leaf extracts [34]. Advances in FTIR can trace out significant changes in food composition that may be of harmful extraneous material [35]. Near-Infrared Spectroscopy and Chemometrics are used in the classification and quantification of the adulteration in pure olive oil by soya oil, sun flower oil, corn oil, walnut oil and hazelnut oil [36].

Development of high-field NMR spectrometers provided the possibility of recording two- and multi- dimensional NMR spectra, detecting NMR of different nuclei, and using “nano” probes for microliter quantities of sample makes it possible to analyse complex mixtures at the molecular level [37-38]. This is particularly useful in detecting the adulteration in liquid products like wine, fruit Juices (eg. orange and grape) that are adulterated with sugar solution, citric and tartaric acid, and colorants or cheaper juices originating from other fruits. Atomic absorption spectroscopy is used in the determination of the animal source origin for meat products based on the mineral composition [39]. ELISA (Enzyme Linked Immunosorbent assay) are the most common techniques used to detect foreign protein in the milk products and PAGE (Polyacrylamide Gel Electrophoresis) are usually used to detect milk from different species as adulterants in milk of a particular species [40].

4. DNA Barcoding and Metabarcoding

DNA barcoding and metabarcoding are some of the advance innovative analytical methods for plant identification at species level. The HPLC-MS though provide a quantitative and qualitative information's to enable the identification and quantification of the chemical compounds, but does not always offer accurate identification of the species. On the other hand, DNA based methods (barcoding and metabarcoding) offer an accurate identification of the species but does not offer any information about the quality and quantity of the secondary metabolites. Therefore, these two techniques are used together and complement each other in detecting the species identity and the chemical composition of the biological

samples [41]. The analysis and the identification of species in mixtures can be solved only by using DNA metabarcoding and not DNA barcoding. DNA metabarcoding will allow the simultaneous detection of species from processed mixtures (pills, capsules, powder, extracts, oil, teas, etc.). Whereas, the DNA barcoding can detect the single species, which may be even powdered or an extract [42].

Conclusion

Though industries make efforts to provide good products to their customers but knowingly or unknowingly, adulterations brings down the quality of the products in the food and herbal drug industry. To sort out such issues, a complete knowledge of medicinal plants, in the aspect of what is adulterated with what? Only then, one can think about what kind of techniques can be used further for the detection of adulteration in a particular product or species. Extensive application and use of sophisticated techniques like HPLC and DNA barcoding can be an economic concern for an individual and industries. Therefore, with complete knowledge of adulteration, one can try with small and simple cost-effective techniques (eg. morphology, microscopy, etc.) as a first step to identify the appropriate adulterant, before using the sophisticated analysis that are usually much costlier. Also, it is important that researchers working on a particular plant species should consider creating an extensive information on the adulterants as well. Such an approach can lead to creating suitable and cost-effective techniques (eg. species/product specific kit or protocols for identification) that will greatly help in the fight against adulterations.

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